

Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units

Residential Buildings in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

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Abstract

This work is related to Heat Index in the context of thermostatic control of air conditioning units.

Heat Index is the temperature equivalent of the discomfort caused by the air temperature and the relative humidity (RH).

Usually, the air conditioning systems are set to a much lower temperature than needed, resulting in overcooling (which for many people causes discomfort and health hazards) and waste of energy.

This work determines the Heat Index which is comfortable enough and does not waste energy for overcooling, called here “*Comfort Heat Index*”. The Comfort Heat Index is 26.6°C (79.9°F).

Setting air conditioning systems to a Comfort Heat Index (CHI) will provide air conditioning that is comfortable enough for those suffering from heat and much better for those suffering from cold.

The work also introduces the Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).

Based on the analyzed data for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, the Heat Index remains below the Comfort Heat Index at cooling setpoints below 25.5°C in Jerusalem and 25.7°C in Tel Aviv.

The work applies the Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Online program (BESOO) version 522 which, in addition to previous versions, also calculates the Heat Index of air conditioned room.

Glossary

Ave	average
CHI	Comfort Heat Index = 26.6°C (79.9°F)
dtau	time period of the integration = integration interval, sec
HI	temperature equivalent of the discomfort caused by the air temperature and the air relative humidity (RH), °C, (°F)
HIO	Heat Index(HI) above Comfort Heat Index (CHI) not in Cooling or Heating hours, while Heat-On below 24°C, °C
OCAC	Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning – setting of air conditioning thermostat that results in minimum air conditioning hours, minimum energy consumption, and in Heat Index below the Comfort Heat Index (26.6°C)
RH	relative humidity of air, %
Ta	ambient (outside) air temperature, °C
Tr	room air temperature, °C
TTC	Thermal Time Constant, hours

Energy Units

Generally, this work is in metric units. Calculations and application of Heat Index involve degrees of Fahrenheit. Energy is expressed in Joule (J) or Watt-second (Ws) and kWh, and power in Watts.

Heat Index – Air Humidity Temperature Equivalent

The Heat Index (HI) is the air humidity discomfort temperature equivalent, °C (or °F).

Following is the official definition of the Heat Index as on the NOAA site [1]:

“The Heat Index is a measure of how hot it really feels when relative humidity is factored in with the actual air temperature. To find the Heat Index temperature, look at the Heat Index Chart above or check our Heat Index Calculator. As an example, if the air temperature is 96°F and the relative humidity is 65%, the heat index--how hot it feels--is 121°F. The red area without numbers indicates extreme danger.

Since heat index values were devised for shady, light wind conditions, exposure to full sunshine can increase heat index values by up to 15°F. Also, strong winds, particularly with very hot, dry air, can be extremely hazardous”.

Heat Index Online Calculators

This work uses the following Heat Index online calculators:

- NOAA - National Weather Service [5]
- ISGlobal - The Barcelona Institute for Global Health [6]
- Calculator.net - Heat Index Calculator [8]

ISGlobal [6] and Calculator.net [8] also indicate the comfort Heat Index.

Determination of Comfort Heat Index Using Dew Point

The NOAA - National Weather Service website [3] includes the following definition of the comfort and discomfort levels using dew point:

General comfort levels USING DEW POINT that can be expected during the summer months:

- less than or equal to 55: dry and comfortable
- between 55 and 65: becoming "sticky" with muggy evenings
- greater than or equal to 65: lots of moisture in the air, becoming oppressive

The above definition clearly states that a dew point less than or equal to 55°F (12.77°C) is comfortable.

Heat Index Categories

NOAA - National Weather Service – Heat Index Categories

The site "[Weather.gov > Location > Heat Index Chart](#)" [4] includes the following table:

Table 1 - NOAA - Possible heat disorders for people in high risk groups [5]

Category	Heat Index	Possible heat disorders for people in high risk groups
Extreme Danger	130°F or higher (54°C or higher)	Heat stroke or sunstroke likely.
Danger	105 - 129°F (41 - 54°C)	Sunstroke, muscle cramps, and/or heat exhaustion likely. Heatstroke possible with prolonged exposure and/or physical activity.
Extreme Caution	90 - 105°F (32 - 41°C)	Sunstroke, muscle cramps, and/or heat exhaustion possible with prolonged exposure and/or physical activity.
Caution	80 - 90°F (27 - 32°C)	Fatigue possible with prolonged exposure and/or physical activity.

The NOAA tables [4] start at 80°F, which may indicate that Heat Index below 80°F is comfortable.

Table 2 - ISG – HI categories, °C [6]

WARNING	HEAT INDEX	HEALTH IMPACT
Safe	< 26	No adverse effects expected due to heat
Caution	27- 32	Fatigue possible with prolonged exposure and/or physical activity
Extreme Caution	33 - 40	Heat stroke, heat cramps or heat exhaustion possible with prolonged exposure and/or physical activity
Danger	41 - 51	Heat cramps or heat exhaustion likely and heat stroke possible with prolonged exposure and/or physical activity
Extreme Danger	52 - 92	Heat stroke highly likely
Beyond human threshold*	<93	Values beyond human resistance to heat

The above table indicates a Heat Index below 26°C as “Safe”, which may be considered comfortable.

Table 3 - HI categories – corrected ISG, °C

Category	Original NOAA Table		ISG		corrected ISG			
	from °F	to °F	from °C	to °C	from °C	to °C		
Safe					<26.00	<26.67		
Caution	80	90	26.67	32.22	27.00	32.00	26.67	<32.22
Extreme Caution	90	105	32.22	40.56	33.00	40.00	32.22	<40.56
Danger	105	129	40.56	53.89	41.00	51.00	40.56	<53.89
Extreme Danger	>=130		>=54.44		52.00	92.00	53.89	<=92.00
Beyond human threshold					<93		>92.00	

According to the above tables the safe upper Heat Index limit is 26.67°C, 80°F.

Table 4 - HI categories – Calculator.net, °C [8]

Category	from °C	to °C
Comfortable		<27
Caution	27	31
Extreme caution	32	40
Danger	41	54
Extreme danger	=>55	

According to calculator.net Heat Index categories, the comfortable upper limit is below 27°C.

Table 5 - Calculator.net – example of comfort HI, °F [8]

Heat Index Temperature: **80°F** (27°C or 300K)

Air Temperature: 80 Fahrenheit °F
 Relative Humidity: 40 %
 Calculate Clear

In the above example the comfort HI is 80°F, however, when converted to centigrade, it is 27°C and not 26.7°C.

Running the same set of data on the NOAA calculator [5] brings more accurate results:

Table 6 - Comfort Heat Index example on NOAA calculator [5]

Air Temperature: 80 °F 26.67 °C
 Relative Humidity: 40 %
 Calculate Reset
 Heat Index = 79.9 F / 26.6 C

The dew point of the above set of data is 53.5°F (11.9°C), well below the NOAA definition of comfortable Heat Index [3]:

less or equal to 55°F: dry and comfortable

Determination of Comfort Heat Index Using Heat Index Categories

According to the above tables and calculators, HI below 80°F is comfortable.

The above example of Ta 80°F and RH 40% shows that Heat Index of 79.9°F is regarded as comfortable. Conversion of 79.9°F to Centigrade results in 26.6111°C.

This determines the limit of the comfort HI to 79.9°F and 26.6°C.

Table 7 - Comfort Heat Index

Comfort Heat Index, °F	<=79.9
Comfort Heat Index, °C	<=26.6

BESOO Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Program

Version 512 of BESOO [10] calculates thermal energy to cool room air to a user-defined temperature.

The default “Cool On temperature” is in the 512 program 26°C. The 512 program displays in the simulation result the following data related to air conditioning:

- cooling start date
- cooling end date
- cooling hours in the simulation period
- thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)
- quantity of condense during cooling
- cooling energy for condense
- thermal energy for cooling and for condense

The current version (522) calculates additional parameters related to air conditioning:

- room air average Heat Index (HI) in the cooling hours
- maximum HI in the cooling hours
- minimum HI in the cooling hours
- period of time when the HI is above the Comfort Heat Index (CHI)
- period of time when the HI is below CHI

Cooling stops before 1 November in Jerusalem and before 1 December in Tel Aviv, regardless of the thermostat setting.

The simulation integration interval is 10 seconds.

Table 8 - Heating and cooling periods in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv in version 522

v522	Jerusalem	Ave Ta °C	Tel Aviv	Ave Ta °C
simulation start	01-Jun-23	25.70	01-May-23	17.78
cooling (summer) start	01-Jun-23	25.70	01-May-23	17.78
cooling (summer) end	31-Oct-23	21.64	30-Nov-23	16.26
heating (winter) start	01-Nov-23	21.01	01-Dec-23	16.43
heating (winter) end	31-May-24	18.58	30-Apr-24	21.87
simulation end	31-May-24	18.58	30-Apr-24	21.87

Heat Index Formula

Heat Index is calculated using few formulas.

Formula 1 - Heat Index Steadman's formula for HI<80°F, °F

$$HI = 0.5 * (TF + 61.0 + 1.2*(TF - 68.0) + 0.094*RH)$$

Formula 2 - Heat Index Rothfusz formula for HI=>80°F, °F

$$HI = -42.379 + 2.04901523 * TF + 10.14333127 * RH - 0.22475541 * TF * RH - 0.00683783 * TF * TF - 0.05481717 * RH * RH + 0.00122874 * TF * TF * RH + 0.00085282 * TF * RH * RH - 0.00000199 * TF * TF * RH * RH$$

if (RH<13 and TF>80 and TF<112) :

$$HI = HI - ((13 - RH)/4) * SQRT((17 - ABS(TF-95))/17)$$

if (RH>85 and TF>80 and TF<87) :

$$HI = HI + ((RH - 85)/10) * ((87 - TF)/5)$$

- HI Heat Index – air humidity temperature equivalent, °F
- TF air temperature in Fahrenheit, °F
- RH air relative humidity in % (for humidity 60%, use number 60 and not 0.60)
- SQRT square root
- ABS absolute

Validation of Heat Index Formula Applied in BESOO Programs

The formulas used in BESOO programs were validated by comparing few random sets of data with results of 3 online calculators.

Table 9 - Validation of BESOO Heat Index formulas by comparing with online calculators

°C	RH %	BESOO522	NOAA	ISGlobal	Calculator
16	30	14.44	14.5	13	14
16	50	14.96	15.0	14	15
16	80	15.74	15.8	15	16
18	60	17.42	17.4	17	17
20	50	19.36	19.4	19	19
22	50	21.56	21.6	21	22
24	50	23.76	23.8	24	24
26	40	25.70	25.7	25	26
28	30	27.10	27.1	27	27
30	10	27.86	27.9	28	28
30	25	28.44	28.5	29	28
30	90	40.77	40.8	43	41
32	25	30.32	30.3	31	30
36	25	35.05	35.1	35	35
40	25	41.08	41.1	41	41
44	10	41.06	41.0	41	41
44	30	51.73	51.8	52	52
44	50	69.26	69.3	76	69
44	90	124.85	125.0	111	125

Small differences between the BESOO programs and NOAA are the result of a lower precision of the NOAA calculator.

The Heat Index formulas in BESOO programs were successfully validated.

Meteorological Data

The data sets for ambient air temperature, relative humidity (RH) and global solar radiation are from the Israel Meteorological Service website (<https://ims.gov.il>). The records are for every 10 minutes. The data sets are for the years 2023 and 2024. Global solar radiation is multiplied by conversion factors according to the direction of the outer wall, month and hour.

The conversion factor is from the “*Hourly Solar Radiation at Selected Tilt Angles and Directions in Tel Aviv*” internet site (<https://nowagreen.com/se>).

The simulation starts in Spring 2023 and ends in Spring 2024.

The Building and the Apartment

The calculations are for the entire apartment and not for individual rooms; the entire apartment is considered one room.

It is assumed that the room temperature in all neighboring apartments is the same as in the tested apartment. Windows are not considered.

Chart 1 - Building and apartment

Default Input Values

Table 10 - Default input values for Jerusalem

choose direction of part 1:	<input type="text" value="ESS"/>
choose direction of part 2:	<input type="text" value="SWW"/>
Heat On temperature	<input type="text" value="19"/> °C
Cool On temperature	<input type="text" value="26"/> °C
infiltration - number of changes per hour	<input type="text" value="0.1"/> V/hr
ventilation - number of changes per hour	<input type="text" value="10"/> V/hr
Winter ventilation ambient temperature (Ta) >	<input type="text" value="21"/> °C
Winter Δ (Ta - Troom) >	<input type="text" value="1"/> °C
Summer ventilation Ta <	<input type="text" value="24"/> °C
Summer Δ (Troom - Ta) >	<input type="text" value="1"/> °C
height between floors (outside)	<input type="text" value="3.00"/> m
room height (inside)	<input type="text" value="2.65"/> m
floor length of outside wall part 1	<input type="text" value="10"/> m
floor length of outside wall part 2	<input type="text" value="10"/> m
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	<input type="text" value="0.100"/> m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	<input type="text" value="0.020"/> m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	<input type="text" value="0.200"/> m
inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	<input type="text" value="0"/> m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	<input type="text" value="0.015"/> m

Simulation Results Table

Table 11 - Simulation results table for default input values in Jerusalem

15/10/2025 06:51:50 GMT			
nowagreen.com BESOO page 522Jm, v522Jm.01 Comfort Heat Index (CHI), limited cooling period_thermostatic control			
HeatT/CoolT	19	26	°C
URL	https://nowagreen.com/BESO/522Jm		
Integration Interval	10	sec	dtau
Thermal Time Constant	109.61	hours	TTC
start day	20230531		
last day	20240531		
simulation days	367		
Ave ambient air temperature in the simulation period	18.59	°C	
Ave ambient air RH in the simulation period	62%		
simulation hours	8808		100%
total energy for heating, cooling and condense	1105	kWh thermal	
Heating			
heating start date	20231128		
heating end date	20240327		
heating hours in the simulation period	1769		20%
Ave ambient air temperature in heating period	11.8	°C	
Ave ambient air RH in heating period	70%		
thermal energy for heating	396	kWh thermal	36%
Max Heat power [W thermal]	680	20240203	8:40
Cooling			
cooling start date	20230602		
cooling end date	20231029		
cooling hours in the simulation period	924		10%
Ave ambient air temperature in cooling period	23.67	°C	
Ave ambient air RH in cooling period	58%		
thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)	346	kWh thermal	31%
quantity of condense during cooling	529	liter of water	
cooling energy for condense	364	kWh thermal	33%
thermal energy for cooling and for condense	710	kWh thermal	64%
Max Cool power [W thermal]	773	20230908	19:40
Max power for condense [W thermal]	1296	20230729	18:50
Max power for cooling and for condense	2069	W thermal	
HI = Heat Index			
Ave Heat Index (HI) in cooling hours	25.73	°C	AveHIC
duration of Heat Index in cooling hours	929	hours	11%
Max Heat Index in cooling hours °C	28.26	20230813	22:00
Min Heat Index in cooling hours °C	24.92	20230728	11:20
Ave Heat Index above Comfort HI (CHI) in cooling hours	27.69	°C	AveHICup
duration of Heat Index above CHI in cooling hours	30	hours	0%
Ave Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	25.66	°C	AveHICdn
duration of Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	899	hours	10%
HIO = (HI>CHI) not in Cooling or Heating hours with Heat On < 24°C			
Ave HIO above CHI	29.34	°C	AveHIO
duration of HIO above CHI	753	hours	9%
Max HIO above CHI °C	40.24	20240426	16:50
Ventilation			
ventilation in Winter not in Heating hours	60	hours	1%
ventilation in Summer not in Cooling hours	1293	hours	15%
ventilation in Winter and Summer not in Heating or Cooling hours	1353	hours	15%
Comfort hours			
comfort hours without heating or cooling	6115	hours	69%
comfort hours without heating or cooling or ventilation	4762	hours	54%

Simulation Results for 16°C-30°C Cooling Temperature

Table 12 - Simulation results for cooling temperature in range 16°C-30°C in Jerusalem (no heating)

Cool On °C	EC kWh	EW kWh	hrC hr	AveHIC °C	MaxHIC °C	MinHIC °C	AveHICup °C	hrHICup hr	AveHICdn °C	hrHICdn hr	ventS hr
16	3,249	3,082	3,694	15.17	16.24	13.92	0	0	15.17	3,695	1
17	3,001	2,979	3,649	16.26	17.34	15.02	0	0	16.26	3,649	28
18	2,717	2,803	3,542	17.34	18.44	16.12	0	0	17.34	3,543	99
19	2,405	2,563	3,370	18.41	19.54	17.22	0	0	18.41	3,372	209
20	2,061	2,243	3,100	19.45	20.64	18.32	0	0	19.45	3,103	365
21	1,674	1,817	2,748	20.48	21.74	19.42	0	0	20.48	2,753	584
22	1,298	1,397	2,335	21.51	22.84	20.52	0	0	21.51	2,341	806
23	975	1,035	1,938	22.54	23.94	21.62	0	0	22.54	1,945	984
24	698	730	1,537	23.57	24.96	22.72	0	0	23.57	1,544	1,136
25	478	493	1,146	24.62	26.06	23.82	0	0	24.62	1,152	1,252
26	346	364	924	25.73	28.26	24.92	27.69	30	25.66	899	1,293
27	245	259	689	27.04	32.17	26.02	27.49	407	26.41	287	1,315
28	175	186	511	27.71	35.40	26.39	27.72	511	26.48	3	1,323
29	128	138	399	28.36	37.80	27.12	28.36	400	0	0	1,326
30	92	104	344	29.25	37.11	27.86	29.25	345	0	0	1,327

- Cool On cooling activation temperature, °C
- EC thermal energy to reduce room air temperature, kWh thermal/year
- EW thermal energy to remove humidity from room air, kWh thermal/year
- hrC cooling hours, hr/year
- AveHIC average Heat Index (HI) in cooling hours, °C
- MaxHIC maximum Heat Index in cooling hours, °C
- MinHIC minimum Heat Index in cooling hours, °C
- AveHICup average Heat Index in cooling hours when HI > CHI, °C
- hrHICup hours when HI > CHI in cooling hours, hr/year
- AveHICdn average Heat Index in cooling hours when HI < CHI, °C
- hrHICdn hours when HI < CHI in cooling hours, h/year
- ventS ventilation hours in Summer (cooling period)
- CHI Comfort Heat Index 26.6°C (79.9°F)

Table 13 - Simulation results for cooling temperature in range 16°C-30°C in Tel Aviv (no heating)

Cool On °C	EC kWh	EW kWh	hrC hr	AveHIC °C	MaxHIC °C	MinHIC °C	AveHICup °C	hrHICup hr	AveHICdn °C	hrHICdn hr	ventS hr
16	4,833	5,660	5,049	15.47	16.14	13.97	0	0	15.47	5,050	48
17	4,478	5,524	4,976	16.57	17.24	15.07	0	0	16.57	4,979	79
18	4,116	5,347	4,872	17.67	18.34	16.17	0	0	17.67	4,875	123
19	3,746	5,122	4,697	18.77	19.44	17.27	0	0	18.77	4,702	186
20	3,381	4,864	4,513	19.87	20.54	18.37	0	0	19.87	4,518	255
21	3,012	4,557	4,276	20.97	21.64	19.47	0	0	20.97	4,283	342
22	2,637	4,191	3,982	22.07	22.71	20.57	0	0	22.07	3,990	455
23	2,261	3,770	3,633	23.17	23.73	21.67	0	0	23.17	3,643	592
24	1,908	3,338	3,270	24.26	24.83	22.77	0	0	24.26	3,282	729
25	1,582	2,903	2,905	25.36	25.93	23.87	0	0	25.36	2,918	862
26	1,351	2,604	2,727	26.61	28.08	24.97	27.23	770	26.37	1,970	901
27	1,134	2,296	2,550	28.87	31.27	26.15	28.90	2,529	26.47	33	928
28	931	1,980	2,379	30.72	34.23	26.65	30.72	2,389	0	0	946
29	742	1,657	2,174	32.86	37.51	27.37	32.86	2,183	0	0	958
30	571	1,336	1,940	35.3	40.77	28.14	35.30	1,947	0	0	966

In the range 16°C-25°C, there are no cases where the Heat Index (HI) is above the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv. The next tables are for 25°C-26°C cooling temperature range to find the exact point when the room air Heat Index is above the comfort level (CHI).

Table 14 - Simulation results for cooling temperature in range 25°C -26°C in Jerusalem (no heating)

Cool On °C	EC kWh	EW kWh	hrC hr	AveHIC °C	MaxHIC °C	MinHIC °C	AveHICup °C	hrHICup hr	AveHICdn °C	hrHICdn hr	ventS hr
25.0	478	493	1,146	24.62	26.06	23.82	0	0	24.62	1,152	1,252
25.1	463	479	1,122	24.72	26.17	23.93	0	0	24.72	1,129	1,258
25.2	449	465	1,096	24.83	26.28	24.04	0	0	24.83	1,103	1,263
25.3	435	451	1,072	24.94	26.39	24.15	0	0	24.94	1,079	1,267
25.4	421	438	1,048	25.05	26.50	24.26	0	0	25.05	1,055	1,272
25.5	408	425	1,027	25.15	26.61	24.37	26.61	0	25.15	1,034	1,276
25.6	395	412	1,007	25.26	27.11	24.48	26.86	9	25.25	1,005	1,279
25.7	382	400	987	25.38	27.39	24.59	27.25	13	25.35	981	1,283
25.8	369	388	964	25.49	27.68	24.70	27.36	18	25.46	953	1,287
25.9	357	376	943	25.61	27.97	24.81	27.58	23	25.56	926	1,290
26.0	346	364	924	25.73	28.26	24.92	27.69	30	25.66	899	1,293

Table 15 - Simulation results for cooling temperature in range 25°C -26°C in Tel Aviv (no heating)

Cool On °C	EC kWh	EW kWh	hrC hr	AveHIC °C	MaxHIC °C	MinHIC °C	AveHICup °C	hrHICup hr	AveHICdn °C	hrHICdn hr	ventS hr
25.0	1,582	2,903	2,905	25.36	25.93	23.87	0	0	25.36	2,918	862
25.1	1,558	2,874	2,887	25.47	26.04	23.98	0	0	25.47	2,900	867
25.2	1,535	2,844	2,869	25.58	26.15	24.09	0	0	25.58	2,885	871
25.3	1,511	2,814	2,852	25.69	26.26	24.20	0	0	25.69	2,867	875
25.4	1,488	2,785	2,835	25.80	26.37	24.31	0	0	25.80	2,848	879
25.5	1,465	2,755	2,817	25.91	26.48	24.42	0	0	25.91	2,831	883
25.6	1,442	2,725	2,799	26.02	26.59	24.53	0	0	26.02	2,813	887
25.7	1,419	2,695	2,782	26.13	27.31	24.64	26.80	11	26.13	2,784	891
25.8	1,396	2,665	2,764	26.25	27.56	24.75	26.91	110	26.23	2,667	894
25.9	1,373	2,635	2,745	26.40	27.82	24.86	27.07	347	26.31	2,412	898
26.0	1,351	2,604	2,727	26.61	28.08	24.97	27.23	770	26.37	1,970	901

Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC)

Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC) refers to the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CFI = 26.6°C).

Based on the analyzed data for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, the Heat Index remained below the Comfort Heat Index at cooling setpoints below 25.5°C in Jerusalem and

25.7°C in Tel Aviv.

Therefore, setting the cooling temperature to 25.4°C in Jerusalem or 25.6°C in Tel Aviv ensures that the Heat Index never exceeds the comfort threshold of 26.6°C. Accordingly, the Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC) temperatures are determined as:

Table 16 - Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), °C

OCAC for Jerusalem, °C	25.4
OCAC for Tel Aviv, °C	25.6

Advantages of OCAC – Jerusalem:

- Heat Index always below CFI (26.6°C)
- ~12% reduction in energy consumption compared to a 25°C setting
- ~9% reduction in cooling operation hours compared to a 25°C setting

Advantages of OCAC – Tel Aviv:

- Heat Index always below CFI (26.6°C)
- ~7% reduction in energy consumption compared to a 25°C setting
- ~4% reduction in cooling operation hours compared to a 25°C setting

Disadvantages of Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning

The tables above show the disadvantages of thermostatic control of air conditioning:

Running the air conditioning below the Comfort Heat Index causes an unnecessary cold air stream and a waste of energy for comfort cooling.

Cooling Discomfort below OCAC

Table 17 - Cooling discomfort and waste of energy below OCAC

Cool On °C	ΔT		ΔhrC		ΔEC	
	Jm °C	TA °C	Jm Hr	TA hr	Jm kWh th	TA kWh th
16	-9.4	-9.6	+252%	+80%	+637%	+152%
17	-8.4	-8.6	+248%	+78%	+596%	+140%
18	-7.4	-7.6	+238%	+74%	+543%	+127%
19	-6.4	-6.6	+222%	+68%	+478%	+113%
20	-5.4	-5.6	+196%	+61%	+401%	+98%
21	-4.4	-4.6	+162%	+53%	+306%	+82%
22	-3.4	-3.6	+123%	+42%	+214%	+64%
23	-2.4	-2.6	+85%	+30%	+134%	+45%
24	-1.4	-1.6	+47%	+17%	+66%	+26%
25.0	-0.4	-0.6	+9%	+4%	+13%	+8%
25.1	-0.3	-0.5	+7%	+3%	+10%	+6%
25.2	-0.2	-0.4	+5%	+3%	+6%	+5%
25.3	-0.1	-0.3	+2%	+2%	+3%	+4%
25.4	OCOA	-0.2	+0%	+1%	+0%	+3%
25.5		-0.1		+1%		+1%
25.6		OCOA		+0%		+0%

Chart 2 - Cooling discomfort and waste of energy below OCAC - Jerusalem

Chart 3 - Cooling discomfort and waste of energy below OCAC – Tel Aviv

As can be seen from the above tables and charts, lowering the air conditioning temperature below the Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC) and below the Comfortable Heat Index (CHI) has a twofold impact on air conditioning discomfort: lower temperature and more cooling hours.

BESOO Website

This version of the Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization is available online (free, no need to login) on:

<https://nowagreeen.com/BESO/522Jm>

<https://nowagreeen.com/BESO/522TA>

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